

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Milestones

Document info

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Responsible Participant	Alexander Botzki
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*For types of deliverables please see [Guidelines for ELIXIR Commissioned Services](#)

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1	draft	10/11/2024	
1.0.0	Alexander Botzki	23/12/2024	
1.0.1	SPLASH project leads: Alexia Cardona Elin Kronander Alexander Botzki Geert Van Geest Bruna Piereck Moura	29/01/2025	
	Content Check by WP1		
	Content Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

(Remove if not applicable)

ETrP	ELIXIR Training Platform
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Executive Summary

The ELIXIR SPLASH project aims to centralize and showcase the diverse training resources developed by ETrP. By creating a user-friendly digital platform, SPLASH seeks to raise awareness and recognition of training efforts and ensure sustainable, high-quality training practices.

The objective is to enhance the accessibility and long-term impact of ELIXIR Training Platform (ETrP) resources by ensuring consistent and high-quality content. The problem addressed is the inconsistency and dispersion of training resources across different channels, which hampers the comprehensive understanding and utilization of these resources. Milestone M3.4 focuses on the editorial review and feedback of various documentation and pages on the Training SPLASH platform to ensure content consistency across all pages.

The milestone was successfully achieved following several discussions and workshops with the Training Platform and Training Coordinators. Key meetings included the individual authoring meetings of members of the training platform, the overarching SPLASH review meeting on November 22, 2024, and joint content/technical meetings in December 2024. The specific content of the Training Lifecycle stages and relevant ELIXIR resources are now displayed on the SPLASH website. Future workshops are planned to fine-tune the narrative of each stage and add new relevant resources.

The uniqueness of the Training Lifecycle lies in its role as the first process to consolidate all ETrP products in a centralized, accessible format. The long-term ambition of the SPLASH project is to become a recognised platform for best practices in training within the life sciences and beyond, ultimately setting a new standard for Training. By centralizing these resources, the SPLASH project aims to ensure that training is not only accessible but also conducted with the highest standards of educational expertise, thereby fostering sustainable and impactful training programs across the life sciences field.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

Milestone *M3.4 Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page* is part of the SPLASH project. The output of this milestone was finalised during a SPLASH editorial review meeting on 18th of December. The specific content of the Training lifecycle stages are now displayed on the SPLASH website.

Figure 1: The Training Life Cycle¹

This milestone was achieved after several discussions and workshops with the Training Platform and Training Coordinators after having achieved [M3.1 Consolidate the key components of the ELIXIR Training lifecycle by discussions with Training ExCos and Training Coordinators](#). Subsequent workshops included:

- Offline work of individual pairs for each stage to finalise draft version of each stage

Stage group	Authors
Plan stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patricia Palagi • Eva Alloza • Bérénice Batut • Nadja Zlender • Oliver Sand • Daniel Wibberg • Luciana Peixoto • Elin Kronander • Jeanne Wilbrandt • Bruna Piereck • Samantha Wittke
Design stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monique Zahn • Alexia Cardona • Zoltán Gáspári • Loredana Le Pera

¹ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>

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Evaluate stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Elin Kronander ● Kim Gurwitz ● Daniel Wibberg ● Olivier Sand ● Zoltan Gaspari ● Monique Zahn ● Mihail Anton ● Jeanne Wilbrandt ● Alexander Botzki ● Helena Schnitzer

- SPLASH kickoff meeting (22 August 2023)
- SPLASH Training Lifecycle brainstorming meeting (6 October 2023)
- Biohackathon Europe 2023 Project: SPLASH Project (20 October -3 November 2023)
- Training Life Cycle Workshop 1 (22 April 2024)

- Training Life Cycle Workshop 2 (3 May 2024)
- SPLASH review meeting (22 November 2024)
- SPLASH joint content/technical meeting 1 (11 December 2024)
- SPLASH joint content/technical meeting 2 (18 December 2024)
- SPLASH Editorial meeting (18 December 2024)
- add specific activities for D4.3

In 2025 and 2026, further workshops are planned to finetune the narrative of each stage, working towards *D3.1 A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps, connected to the various documents/SOPs/Best practices.*